

COMPUTATION OF ACTIVE CLAY CONTENT USING ATTERBERG LIMITS PARAMETERS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an analysis of more than 300 Atterberg limit and clay content test results collected from the literature. The correlation between the Atterberg limits and active clay is discussed. Simple models of computing active clay content are presented. The proposed models were found to estimate the active clay content within the statistical testing bound of ± 12 given in AASHTO T88-10.

INTRODUCTION

Skempton (1953) defined 'activity' as the ratio of plasticity index (PI) to < 0.002 mm clay fraction. As defined by Skempton, the clay 'activity' includes both inactive and active clay content. Based on the clay 'activity', he classified clays into three groups: inactive clay with 'activity' of less than 0.75, normal clay with 'activity' in the range of 0.75 to 1.25, and active clay with 'activity' of more than 1.25. In this study, the clay is divided into only two groups, namely active and inactive clay. Active clay is the one that imparts plasticity to the soil. In contrast, inactive clay does not impart plasticity to the soil but is classified as clay based on particle size.

In accordance with BS 1377 and AASHTO T88-10, all soil particles with a diameter of less than $2 \mu\text{m}$ are defined as clay. Therefore, these standard procedures determine total clay content, which includes both active (cohesive) and inactive (cohesionless) clay. Based on the definition of clay, a finely grounded non-plastic cohesionless rock flour, a non-clay mineral, is classified as clay if its particle sizes are less than $2 \mu\text{m}$. Therefore, the usefulness of the clay content determination is reduced since the test is unable to separate the active from the inactive clay. The reproducibility of clay content determination test results in accordance with AASHTO T88-10 is 12%.

Because of the inclusion of inactive and active clay during the determination of the clay content, the correlation between the liquid limit or plasticity index and clay content is challenging or impossible to model mathematically. However, if the inactive

clay is isolated from the active clay, it is possible to model the correlation between the active clay content and plasticity index mathematically, owing to the fact that the plasticity is imparted to the soil by the presence of active clay within the soil matrix.

This paper presents simple models that can be used to compute the soil's active clay content using the plasticity index and average slope of the British fall cone curve as defined in equation (1) (Maregesi, 2023). 260 Atterberg limits and clay content test results collected from the literature were analyzed, and 115 selected test results whose plasticity index was higher than its clay content were used for developing models of computing the active clay content (Reddy et al. (2020) -45 test results, Cerato et al. (2006) -4 test results, Prakash et al. (2012) - 9 test results, Sridharan et al.,(2000) - 4 test results, Vincent et al. (2021) -6 test results, Otoko (2014)- 12 test results, Widjaja et al. (2020)- 21 test results, Sridharan et al. (1986)-7 test results, Spagnoli et al. (2018) - 76 test results and Afolagboye et al. (2021) - 75 test results. The models were validated using 57 test results collected from the literature and were to predict the active clay content within the statistical testing bound of ± 12 given in AASHTO T88-10.

$$Av. Slope = \frac{20}{LL} \dots \dots (1)$$

Where,

LL is the British fall cone liquid limit.

THE ATTERBERG LIMITS AND CLAY CONTENT

Since active clay imparts plasticity to the soil, an increase in the active clay content is associated with an increase in the liquid limit and plasticity index. The rate of increase of the liquid limit and plasticity of soil depends on the type of clay minerals in the soil. The activeness of the clay depends on the type of clay mineral. Montmorillonite is the most active mineral, followed by illite, and kaolinite clay is the least active mineral. Figure 1 shows the variation of clay content and the plasticity index for the test results analyzed during this study, from which it can

be seen that there is no correlation between the plasticity index and the clay content. It is evident that as the plasticity index increases, the clay content also increases. However, no definite pattern can be established to estimate the clay content based only on the plasticity index of the soil.

Figure 1: The variation of plasticity index and clay content

DEVELOPMENT OF MODEL OF COMPUTING CLAY CONTENT

Casagrande cup and fall cone methods of determining the liquid limits give different values of liquid limit and plasticity index. However, in this study, it has been assumed that both methods yield the same results.

The plasticity of the soil is due to the presence of active clay minerals within the soil matrix; therefore, the plasticity is correlated to the active clay content within the soil matrix. The plasticity index cannot be directly used to estimate the soil's clay content within the soil matrix because the method used for clay content determinations determines both active and inactive clay content (the clay is classified based on the size, BS 1377 and AASHTO T88-10), as evidenced by the scattering of the results, as shown in Figure 1.

The average slope of the fall cone flow curve defined in equation (1) can be used to estimate the plasticity index of inorganic soil and is also a simple indicator of the mineralogical composition of the

soil (Maregesi, 2023). The soil with an average fall cone slope of less than 0.16 is classified as montmorillonite. The average fall cone slope of kaolinite is more than 0.56. The mixed and illite clay mineral plots within the average fall cone slope range of 0.16 to 0.56 (Maregesi, 2023). The relationship between the average fall cone slope and the plasticity index of the test results analyzed during this study is shown in Figure 2. It can be seen that the average slope of the fall cone curve correlates quite well with the plasticity index of the soil as fitted using a power function (equation 2) with a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.9973.

$$PI = 6.4062 \left(\frac{20}{LL} + 0.01 \right)^{-1.42} \dots \dots (2)$$

Where

PI is the plasticity index, and LL is the liquid limit.

Since the plasticity index is highly correlated to the average slope of the average fall cone curve (Figure 2) and the plasticity index is imparted to the soil by the presence of active clay within the soil matrix, then the active clay content must also be correlated to the average slope of the fall cone. Analogously, the inactive clay content is not correlated to the soil's plasticity index because it does not impart plasticity to the soil.

It is hypothesized that for the clay to be classified as active, one percent of active clay within the soil matrix must at least impart one unit of plasticity to the soil. In other words, the plasticity index of the active clay must be greater or equal to the clay content of the soil, which can be expressed mathematically as $PI - \text{Clay} \geq 0$. In case the determined clay content of the soil is more than its plasticity index, then the additional clay content is due to the presence of inactive cohesionless non-clay minerals, which do not contribute to the plasticity of the soil.

Figure 2: The relationship between the average fall cone slope and the plasticity index of the soil

Figure 3: Relationship between the fall cone slope and arithmetic difference between the plasticity index and clay content ($R^2=0.9151$)

Figure 4: The relationship between the average fall cone slope and $PI-Clay \geq 0$ ($R^2=0.9911$).

Figure 5: The variation between the average fall cone slope and $PI-Clay < 0$.

Figure 3 shows the relationship between the average fall cone slope(20/LL) and PI-Clay. As hypothesized above, the PI-Clay is highly correlated to the average slope of the fall cone flow curve, as evidenced by the coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.9151 fitted using the reciprocal quadratic function shown in Equation 3. It can be seen that

the correlation between the average fall cone slope and PI-clay is very good. However, it is evident that below PI-clay= 0, the correlation becomes very poor. Therefore, the relationship between the average fall cone slope and PI-Clay can be divided into two distinct sections: section 1, which is the PI-Clay ≥ 0 , and section 2, which is the PI-Clay < 0 . Figure 4 shows the first section in which Pi-Clay ≥ 0 , from which it can be seen that the correlation of average fall cone slope and PI-clay ≥ 0 is very good, as evidenced by the coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.9911 when fitted using the power function shown in equation 4. In this section, the clay content contributes fully to the plasticity index of the soil; therefore, the section with PI-Clay ≥ 0 , represents the presence of active clay minerals within the soil matrix. Figure 5 shows the second section in which the PI-Clay < 0 , from which it can be seen that there is no correlation between the plasticity index and PI-clay. This section contains inactive non-clay (cohesionless) and active clay minerals. Therefore, equation 3 is a poor predictor of the clay content, but equation 5 can be used to compute the amount of active clay within the soil matrix.

$$PI - Clay = -3.7876 - \frac{737.572}{LL} + 0.0014LL^2 \dots (3)$$

$$PI - Clay = 0.4429 \left(\frac{20}{LL} + 0.03794 \right)^{-2.633} \dots (4)$$

Making clay a subject in equation 4, the active clay content can be computed using equation 5.

$$Clay = PI - \left(0.4429 \left(\frac{20}{LL} + 0.03794 \right)^{-2.633} \right) \dots (5)$$

COMPUTATION OF THE ACTIVE CLAY CONTENT WITHIN THE SOIL MATRIX

As shown in Figure 4, equation 5 can be used to compute the active clay content using two parameters, namely, the plasticity index and the liquid limit. The active clay content for all soils shown in Figure 4 with PI-Clay ≥ 0 was computed using Equation 5. The residual plot is shown in Figures 6 and 7, from which it can be seen that the proposed model predicts the active clay content reasonably well, with 90% of the results plotting within the statistical testing bound of ± 12 .

Figure 6: Residuals plot showing the difference between the determined and computed clay

Figure 7: Comparison between determined and computed clay content

VALIDATION OF THE MODEL USING DATA FROM THE LITERATURE

The proposed model given in equation 5 was validated using 57 Atterberg and clay content results collected from the literature (Mishra et al. (2012) -13 test results, Reznik - 5 test results, Karakan (2022) – 34 test results, Sridharan et al.

(1988)- 5 test results). The validation of the model was carried out using test results whose PI-Clay \geq 0. Figure 8 shows the determined active clay content and the residual, which is the arithmetic difference between the determined and computed clay content. It can be seen that 53 out of 57 test result are within the statistical testing bound of the clay content determination as given in AASHTO-88, suggesting that the proposed model is very robust and can be used for computing the active clay content. If the total clay content is known (determined in accordance with BS 1377 or AASHTO T-88), then the model can be used to compute the active clay content so that the quantity of both inactive and active clay content can be reported.

Figure 8: Residuals plot showing the difference between the determined and computed clay

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE ACTIVE CLAY CONTENT AND ATTERBERG LIMITS

The active clay within the soil matrix imparts plasticity to the soil. Therefore, the active clay content is correlated to the liquid limit and the plasticity index of the soil. Equation 5 can be used to compute active clay content using two parameters, namely the plasticity index and the liquid limit. For the data used during the development of this model, the plasticity index is correlated to the liquid limit such that the plasticity index can be estimated using equation 2; thus, substituting equation 2 into equation 5 results in equation 6. Therefore, the relationship between liquid limit and clay content can be estimated using

Equation 6, which suggests that the clay content can be calculated using liquid limit as the sole predictor.

$$clay = \frac{6.462}{(0.01 + \frac{20}{LL})^{1.42}} - \frac{0.4429}{(0.03794 + \frac{20}{LL})^{2.633}} \dots (6)$$

Figure 9 shows the correlation between the liquid limit and the active clay with the best curve fitted using Equation 6. It can be seen that for the active clay to be 100%, the liquid limit of the soil is supposed to be at least 500. Figure 9 shows that up to the liquid limit of about 120 and active clay content of about 50, the relationship between liquid limit and active clay content can be modeled linearly, as shown in Figure 10 and Equation 7 with a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.956. Therefore, the percentage of active clay within the soil matrix can be estimated using liquid limit as a sole predictor variable.

$$Clay = 0.4227(LL) \dots (7)$$

Figure 11 shows a correlation between the plasticity index and active clay content, from which it can be seen that the active clay content within the soil matrix can be estimated from the plasticity index of the soil. If the active clay content in the soil is 100%, then the plasticity index will be at least 400. The correlation between the active clay and the plasticity index is fitted using the logarithm equation shown in equation 8 with a coefficient of determination of 0.9277.

$$Active\ clay = 23.066 \ln(PI) - 50.853 \dots (8)$$

Figure 11 shows that up to a plasticity index of 100, the plasticity index is linearly correlated with the active clay content; therefore, it can be modeled linearly using equation 9 with a coefficient of determination of (R^2) of 0.9891 (Figure 12).

$$clay = 0.7622(PI) \dots (9)$$

No meaningful correlation was established between the plastic limit and the active clay content (Figure 13).

Figure 9: The relationship between the liquid limit and clay content (for soil whose $PI-Clay > 0$)

Figure 11: The relationship between the plasticity index and active clay content (for soil whose $PI-Clay > 0$)

Figure 10: The relationship between the liquid limit and clay content (for soil whose $PI-Clay > 0$, $R^2 = 0.956$)

Figure 12: The relationship between the plasticity index and active clay content (for soil whose $PI-Clay > 0$, $R^2 = 0.9891$)

Figure 13: The relationship between the plastic limit and active clay content (for soil whose $PI-Clay > 0$)

CONCLUSION

Analysis of Atterberg limits and clay content test results using the soil of different geological originals and geographical regions collected from more than thirteen authors revealed that active clay content is correlated to both liquid limit and plasticity index.

The proposed model established during this study can be used to compute the active clay content for soil whose $PI-Clay \geq 0$, and for soil whose $PI-Clay < 0$ contains both active and inactive clay. Therefore, the proposed models can be used to compute the active clay content such that it will be possible to report both active and inactive clay during clay content determination.

For soil with a liquid limit of less than 125, the active clay content is linearly correlated to the liquid limit. Beyond the liquid limit of more than 125, the relationship between the liquid limit and the clay content is non-linear.

The active clay content was also found to be highly correlated to the plasticity index of the soil; at the plasticity index of less than 100, the active clay content is correlated to the plasticity index; at the plasticity index of more than 100, the plasticity index and active clay content are non-linearly correlated. Based on the achieved coefficient of determination (R^2), which measures the goodness of fit, the plasticity index model predicts the active

clay content more accurately than the liquid limit model.

This study suggests that the clay is active only when its plasticity index exceeds its clay content ($PI-Clay \geq 0$). If the clay content of the soil is more than its plasticity index, then part of the clay content is due to the presence of inactive clay within the soil matrix, which does not contribute to the plasticity of the soil.

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